

**CASTLE ISLAND,
Lough Key, Co. Roscommon**

Priority Enabling Works – Method Statement
CMF 2025 Stream 3 - Application
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1.0 INTRODUCTION

This statement has been prepared as supporting documentation for the Community Monuments Fund 2025 Stream 3 application for funding for enabling works to facilitate safe access to the island to undertake surveys associated with the development of a Conservation Management Plan for Castle Island, Lough Key, Co. Roscommon.

Proposed works include identify and stabilising isolated areas of masonry that are vulnerable to collapse (focusing on wall heads), vegetation clearance to enable detailed surveys of the condition and phasing of the standing masonry ruins and the creation of a temporary shelter on the island for Health and Safety for consultants and contractors working on the island.

There are 3 x Recorded Monuments on Castle Island, which are protected under the National Monuments Acts:

- RO006-046---- Ringfort Cashel – Castle Island Td.
- RO006-046001- Castle- Towerhouse – Castle Island Td.
- RO006-046002- Slip Way – Lough Key Td.

A significant body of research on the island has been collated in recent years. The following is a summary of the history based on this research.

(Extract from Report rock19EO348 Interim, Dr. Tomas Finan, St Louis University)

The Rock of Lough Key, the MacDermot caput in the lordship of Moylurg in the middle ages, is first identified in historical records in the mid twelfth century when the MacDerot lords were given possession of Moylurg by O’Conor overlords. From that point forward, the Rock is mentioned numerous times throughout the Irish annals as the center of MacDermot lordship. The site was the location of a number of major events, such as a devastating fire that killed dozens of people in the late 12th century, a siege undertaken by the Justiciar in early 13th century, and a number of deaths of MacDermot lords and their wives. The site was built up and destroyed a number of times, sometimes by the MacDermot lords themselves in advance of encroachment by other Gaelic families or the Dublin government. Ultimately, the Rock was functionally out of use in the early seventeenth century when the area around Lough Key was granted to the King family. However, a bardic poem dating to the sixteenth century laments that the Rock was not occupied and had fallen into ruin.

Architectural analysis of the Rock in 2008 for the first time identified multiple building phases within the extant stone structures on the island, suggesting that while the standing remains superficially appear to be the 19th century folly designed for the King family, that folly actually hides an earlier fourteenth or fifteenth century tower, which was added to what was presumed to be a cashel enclosure around the island. The enclosure, it was argued, dates to the high middle ages, perhaps as early as the twelfth century.

2.0 CURRENT CONDITION

There is a growing body of research and analysis of archaeology findings on the island and through the work of Dr Tomas Finan this research and analysis is ongoing. This has enabled the proposed team to develop a deep understanding of the island, its significances, challenges and opportunities.

At Castle Island the usual challenges for sites and structures of this type exist, including extensive vegetation, high level masonry instability, reduced stability due to loss of floor and roof restraint and failure of heads to main window and door openings.

Additionally there is the remote island location which requires consideration to ensure works are planned and can be safely and efficiently progressed.

From initial inspections and an outline review of existing information the following priority issues have been identified:

- Standing structures are heavily overgrown with vegetation
- Local areas of precarious high level masonry
- Severe cracking visible and areas of masonry are vulnerable to collapse
- The island is not accessible to the public due to Health and Safety concerns
- It is clearly a very significant archaeological site but no holistic plan for the future of the site exists

Photographs of the existing condition are included in Appendix A

3.0 METHOD STATEMENT

3.1 Nature and Purpose of Purposed Works

Proposed works include identifying and stabilising isolated areas of masonry that are vulnerable to collapse (focusing on wall heads), vegetation clearance to enable detailed surveys of the condition and phasing of the standing masonry ruins and the creation of a temporary shelter on the island for Health and Safety for consultants and contractors working on the island.

3.2 Proposed Project Team

The following are the proposed core project team who will work collaboratively with the client/owner and all stakeholders

Conservation Architect: Aoife Leonard BSc (Hons) BArch (Hons) Dip Arch RIBA AABC
RIAI Grade 1 Conservation Architect

Archaeologist: Dr. Tomas Finan, PhD, FSA

Conservation Structural Engineer: Jon Avent, BSc(Hons) CEng MIStructE IHBC
CARE Accredited Conservation Engineer

Ecologist: Dr. Caroline Shiel, B.Sc., Ph.D

3.3 Methodology

From initial inspections the need for an urgent phase of conservation works has been identified. Priorities include attention to local areas of precarious high level masonry, vegetation control and structural movement to main walls. The progressive nature of these issues means that a significant risk to the building fabric exists and any opportunities to progress elements of urgent works will benefit considerably the evolving strategy for protection of the site.

The approach and strategy would follow accepted best practice guidance ensuring the very lightest of touch to make-safe and protect the structures.

A further drone survey accompanied by a visual survey from ground level will be undertaken to identify precarious areas of masonry. Once areas requiring works have been confirmed

the details of access to undertake the works will be agreed with project team and all stakeholders. Masonry will be recorded and stabilised in original positions where possible by stitching / pinning and rebedding with lime mortar. If, as works progress it is decided that any stones need to be temporarily removed (for H&S reasons) they will be fully recorded, by photographic and drawn survey, and stored for relaying in original positions as part of future works to the conserve the structures.

Vegetation clearance will be undertaken in stages as accepted best practice guidance. Ecological surveys will be undertaken initially and the recommendations from these incorporated into the strategy for vegetation clearance. Works will be programmed to avoid bird nesting season. Plants and climbers growing adjacent to the structures will be cut back to ground level (gradually starting with smaller growth and then larger branches). Vegetation on the structures will be cut back gradually starting at the top and working down. Debris will be removed to an appropriate location off site as it accumulates.

In tandem with these essential priority works consideration has been given to ensuring that works can progress safely and efficiently and recognises the challenges presented by the remote island location. At present there is no shelter or protection available. The small annex roofless single storey kitchen area has been identified as an area where a simple lean-to roof could be formed to provide shelter, material storage and also possible area where meetings, talks or other engagement with interested parties could be facilitated. The construction would involve a minimal structure and be fully reversible should future areas become more accessible.

4.0 IMPACT OF PROPOSED WORKS

MacDermot's Castle is one of County Roscommon's most identifiable landmarks, accessible by boat from the Lough Key Forest & Activity Park tourist centre and a potential tourist destination in its own right. Unfortunately, due to the current state of disrepair the structures could suffer irreversible damage or collapse and the island is not accessible to visitors due to the Health and Safety risks. The proposed works will facilitate safe access for undertaking surveys associated with the development of a Conservation Management Plan. Also the proposed vegetation clearance will enable the standing masonry to be surveyed and assist in building an accurate record of the existing condition and historic development.

These works will greatly benefit the ongoing works to develop a strategy for the future of the island. They will assist the project team in gaining a greater understanding of the standing masonry remains and enable informed decisions to be made on any subsequent conservation works for the site.

**APPENDIX A
PHOTOGRAPHS**

APPENDIX A - PHOTOGRAPHS

Photographs from survey visits in August and November 2024

View of Castle Island from the shore at Lough Key Forest Park

Aerial view looking North

Aerial view looking South

Aerial view

Aerial view looking West

Aerial view looking East

General views showing the current condition of the standing structures on the island

General views showing the current condition of the standing structures on the island

General views showing the current condition of the standing structures on the island

General views showing the current condition of the standing structures on the island

General views showing the current condition of the standing structures on the island

Views (taken with a 3d camera) of the 'kitchen' area as existing - the proposed location of the temporary shelter

APPENDIX B
INTERIM REPORT

MacDermot Rock, Castle Island
July 20, 2024
19E0348

Original licensing for excavation on the Rock of Lough Key was granted in 2019, and subsequent Ministerial Consent was granted as E00548. To maintain consistency, 19E0348 is used throughout this and other correspondence.

Thomas Finan, PhD, FSA

Project Director

John Soderberg, PhD

Associate Project Director

James Schryver, PhD

Associate Project Director

Summary

The interim report on the MacDermot Rock, Castle Island post-excavation work for summer 2024 provides an update on progress achieved with support from the Royal Irish Academy, Saint Louis University, Denison University, and the University of Minnesota Morris. Key areas of focus included completing the phasing of excavations from 2019 to 2023, continuing the analysis of the extensive animal bone assemblage, and maintaining and updating artifact data in line with the National Museum of Ireland standards. Significant achievements include a geological survey identifying stone sources, conservation of 2019 artifacts, and surveys identifying quarrying spots and stone features on the island.

The phasing of the site was based on stratigraphical relationships and rough dating from artifacts, revealing no prehistoric settlement. Notable phases identified include an early medieval cashel wall, a high medieval settlement, and the insertion of a tower house by the MacDermot kings in the late sixteenth century. Victorian modifications by John Nash were also documented. The ongoing animal bone analysis by Dr. John Soderberg highlights remarkable preservation and insights into Gaelic feasting practices. Overall, the report outlines substantial progress towards a final project report due in December 2025 or May 2026, with additional data and analysis to be incorporated in future updates.

I. General Scope of 2024 Effort

With support from the Royal Irish Academy, Saint Louis University, Denison University, and the University of Minnesota Morris, post-excavation analysis of three successful seasons (2019, 2022, 2023) on the Rock of Lough Key continued in the summer of 2024. This summary report is submitted in fulfillment of requirements for the Royal Irish Academy National Committee on Archaeology, as well as fulfilling licensing requirements for National Monuments and the National Museum of Ireland. This report is an update on progress achieved in 2024 and will be supplemented with additional addendums resulting from C14 results, interim animal bone reports, and updates on specialist reports through the academic year 2024-25.

Work in summer 2024 focused on three critically important areas of research related to the overall project. In completing these areas, we have made substantial progress towards our goal of submitting a final project report in December 2025 or May 2026. The Post-Excavation Plan for the Rock of Lough Key, as submitted to the National Committee on Archaeology in December 2023, highlighted several areas that required effort in the new year to meet our final report deadline. Our goals for our summer work, funded by an Archaeology Research Grant by RIA, allowed us to undertake the following:

- Completion of phasing of the three years of excavation
- Continuing analysis of the large animal bone assemblage
- Continuing maintenance and updating of artifact data reflecting standards of NMI

In addition to these goals, multiple other goals were achieved during the academic year or the summer season. Where appropriate, this information will be added to the report in detail.

- A geological survey of the stone on the island was completed by Ronan McCool in late 2023, with a report submitted in early 2024. The report identified likely sources of the various types of stone on the island. It is attached as an appendix to this report.
- Conservation of 2019 artifacts was completed. The 2019 artifacts are now held at the National Museum of Ireland repository.
- A survey of the shore of Lough Key south of Castle Island was completed, identifying quarrying spots for the island. Aerial photos and video were collected, with images as an appendix to this report.
- Assessments of the external enclosing wall continued, with new information provided regarding areas that we feel are in need of immediate attention. A discussion of this information is included in an appendix with photographs.
- Additional survey was carried out on the northern shore of the Rock, identifying stone features that we will argue are slips for boats. We were able to create a more detailed image of the causeway to the mainland, as well as what appears to be a human-made landing area. Photos are included as an appendix.

II. Phasing of the Rock of Lough Key, 2019-2023

Phasing of the site was completed by Thomas Finan and James Schryver in summer 2024. Our phasing is based upon pure stratigraphical relationships, with rough dating applied from artifacts found in particular contexts. We anticipate that the sequence will be refined upon the receipt of C14 dates; for the moment, the Harris Matrix is sound. No evidence of prehistoric settlement or usage has been found on the island.

Phase 1: Entrance Feature

In 2019, an "entrance feature" was identified on the western side of the island on the interior of the extant wall. The feature was initially seen as a break in an early medieval cashel wall found in multiple areas, but upon further review, the entrance feature is an earlier feature than the cashel wall itself, with the walls extending from this feature misaligned to the known locations of the cashel. A large stone was found at the base of this feature (C50); this large stone was below the lake level in 2019, and hence we were unable to continue excavation.

Phase 2: Large Yellow Limestone Deposit

The entrance feature was filled with large (20-30 cm) rounded limestone boulders, distinctive because of their yellow color (C45, C49). In 2022 and 2023, additional contexts of similarly sized and colored boulders (C159, C165, C250, C273) were found. Despite our attempts to disprove the notion, it became clear that these contexts reflected a single deposit (which in Cuttings C-F measured upwards of 2m deep) intentionally placed on the island. The soil matrix of 143 and 144 yielded several pieces of animal bone. Context 254, a dark, silty mud recovered in Cutting F in 2023, extended underneath the wall of the cashel. The context could be seen as the silt remains of soil that settled through the yellow stone deposit over time; alternatively, this soil could be the remnants of a soil matrix deposited with the large yellow stone. I am inclined to believe that the soil is the remains of the surface deposited with the yellow stone. A silver ring-headed pin was recovered in 254, suggesting an early medieval date of approximately 800. Fragmentary pieces of animal bone were found in 254, and we will use these for C14 analysis.

Phase 3: Early Medieval Cashel Wall

An early medieval cashel wall was initially identified in 2019, but further excavations in 2022 and 2023 showed that the cashel wall was likely a replacement for an earlier structure, perhaps represented by the entrance feature in Phase I. The cashel wall was conclusively identified in Cuttings B, C, F, Dn, and G. In all cases, the cashel wall has two faces of coursed stone. The width of the wall was 1.7-2m, and the depth measured in Cutting F in 2023 was 1.97m. The facing stones were typically 20-30cm wide and

10cm thick with no surviving evidence of mortar. The internal fill of the cashel is made up of sub-rounded pebbles and soil. In all cuttings, the cashel wall, when identified, was left in situ. Initially, the Phase I entrance feature was considered a part of the cashel. Essentially, the walls of the cashel do not correspond to the walls found with the Phase I entrance feature and are wholly aligned in a different manner. Further, the yellow boulder fill of Phase II filled the entrance feature, and in no area was this fill found outside of the cashel.

Phase 4: High Medieval Settlement

Clay floor (C5) was put in place directly on top of the extensive burn layer, which in turn was on top of the Phase III cashel wall. In other words, we continue to argue that the inferno that led to the layer of burning corresponds to the historical reference to the great fire on the island in 1185. Whether the smaller entrance was in use in 1185 is unclear; indeed, it would appear that it was not, in retrospect, if only because there is no evidence of burning directly on the stone facing of the entrance. The high medieval settlement on the island in general post-dates the layer of burning that was found in all areas. The features that we believe are associated with this phase are:

1. Building 1
2. Large Entrance Feature
3. Area of Industrial Activity

Clay floor C5 was entirely enclosed by two connected stone walls of identical construction (C4). These walls, on the east and south of the clay floor, were made up of large, 30-40 cm limestone stones, with no evidence of mortar or chiseling. The wall CXX had tipped outward on top of several stones in the wall associated with the Large Entrance Feature, suggesting that the wall at least collapsed after the entrance feature. No evidence of walls were found on the west or northern sides of the clay floor, but a possible robber trench was noted as C6 on the north side.

Within the clay floor C5 several important features were noted. First, a cache of worked antler cores were found on the north east side of the floor. The collection is a complete set of antler in process, with larger antler, antler sliced into cores, antler sliced into rectangular pieces, and finally several pieces that appear to be ready for use in the production of combs.

A flat stone with a deposit of charcoal was found midway in the clay floor on the east-west axis, around 75 cm from the south wall. This was initially considered a fire pit, but its location within the building suggests that it may be the base for a timber support for a roof.

Excavations in 2022 and 2023 in Cuttings C and F were designed to assess the extent of the walls designated as C10 in 2019. A floor surface, C136, composed of extremely large 1.0 m x .75 m flagstones lay directly under the walls C10-C107.

We believe that this feature is a large entrance feature to the island for a number of reasons. First, the facings of the stone walls all face “inward” to the flagstone surface, giving the impression that this was the more important facing aesthetically. Second, upon survey of the external wall after a wall collapse in the winter of

The Entrance Feature leads to the center of the courtyard on the interior of the extant wall, but lies directly on top of the earlier, *cashel* wall (C126). The flagstone slabs of C136 seem to have been intentionally placed on top of the *cashel* wall as a paving surface. However, the flagstones stop abruptly around 3 m from the interior of the *cashel* wall. No discernible floor surface was found to the north east of the flagstone surface, but multiple contexts of burned material and dark, silty soil was noted. A base for a timber was identified as C219; this base was made up of dense burned charcoal small fist sized stones, with several flatter stones inserted as supports for a vertical timber. A flat stone was found at the base, as well as a very large, heavily corroded iron object, possibly an axe.

On the last two days of excavation in 2023 a surface of yellow-orange silty clay appeared on the north-east end of Cutting F. This was left in situ, but an arc of post holes was noted in this surface, and samples from these postholes were collected (C274).

Phase 5: Tower House Insertion

Historically, the tower house was constructed on the island by the MacDermot kings at the latest in 1578. In that year, Brian MacDermot added a "great regal house" to the island, at which a number of great feasts were recorded in the annals, including a feast for all of the great bardic poets of Ireland. Architectural examination of the tower house walls by O’Conor et al. in 2008 argued that the square walls on the interior of the Nash construction were, in fact, the tower house. Supporting this argument was the identification of an arrow slit and a medieval punch-dressed window. The insertion of the tower house likely changed the use pattern on the island, in the sense that the tower became the central area of residence on the island. Building 1 in Phase IV could have been a residential space of some sort. Just as easily, the tower house could have supplanted an earlier structure on the east side of the enclosure wall. Regardless, the artifact "hiatus" from the sixteenth to the nineteenth centuries is notable and corresponds to the construction of the tower. The earliest image of the Rock by Grose in 1791 has been slightly perplexing to some. First, the image shows a square tower and rough stone enclosure wall, and the island seems to be smaller than the modern island. Granted, the image is drawn in a somewhat fanciful manner, with an artificial

landscape of mountains around the lake. Nevertheless, O’Conor and I would argue that the Grose image likely corresponds to the ruined tower and enclosure wall; in other words, at no point was there ever a timber fortification on the island, as argued by many. In 2023, while conducting clearance of brush and trees outside the extant wall for photogrammetry, an interface was noted between stone battering that surrounds the eastern part of the island and the extant wall. This battering has no mortar and is comprised of large, thin stones set at an angle. The soil on this side of the island is very

Grose (1791) Image of Rock of Lough Key; note the square tower house, as well as the stone enclosure.

different in composition from the soil in the enclosure. A resistivity tomography survey conducted in 2017 clearly shows that a great deal of soil was added to the island and that the tower was constructed on top of this soil and, we now know, the extant wall. In other words, the soil on the eastern side of the island was added and enclosed with the stone battering at the same time that the tower house was constructed in the late sixteenth century. The Grose image does not appear to show this area, but does show the stoney area to the north of the island.

The Grose image, drawn before the King-Nash modification to the Rock were made, also shows what might be rudimentary crenelations on the right side of the image in

the foreground relative to the tower. In other words, it would appear that the enclosure wall, in 1791, already had crenellations, while the tower lacked such features.

Phase 6: Victorian Occupation

The Rockingham Estate was awarded to Sir John King in 1603. The grant included Boyle Abbey and surrounding lands, as well as the lands around Lough Key that had been part of the MacDermot lordship of Moylurg. Sir John Bingley was also granted some of these lands. In 1607, King began construction of a residence in Boyle, but it was not until 1771 that the King family began construction of Kingston Hall on the lands to the south of Lough Key. In 1810, Rockingham House supplanted Kingston House as the main residence in Rockingham. A fire destroyed Rockingham House in 1957, with the ruins of the house demolished in the 1970s.

What concerns us for the moment is the 1810 construction of Rockingham House, designed by the noted architect John Nash. Nash, it seems, also offered guidance if not direct design to a reconstruction of the Rock of Lough Key, apparently a ruin from 1600 to 1810. It could have been used for hunting purposes, but little in the way of artifacts from the 17th or 18th centuries were found during excavation.

Nash seems to have designed a folly centered on the tower house constructed by MacDermot. The two wings on either side of the tower were constructed of a mixture of stone and brick, with large neo-gothic windows inserted into the central tower house. The tower and the wings were covered with a concrete facing that continues to deteriorate. The interfaces between the wings and the tower house also continue to deteriorate (see appendix). A kitchen was added to the exterior of the northern side of the extant enclosure wall. Again, the interface between the exterior of this addition is in marked contrast to the extant wall. This kitchen included at least two very large brick-lined ovens, as well as smaller ovens, and had direct access to the lake via a window. The underwater survey by Brady in 2008 identified a massive midden directly outside this kitchen.

As noted, we now believe that the extant wall is essentially a medieval construction. However, it is clear that Nash and/or King added crenellations to the top of the extant wall at the same time that crenellations and a larger single tower were added to the top of the tower house. The extant wall was also modified at this time to provide a clear view northward from the new large windows added to the tower. The modification removed approximately two meters of wall, level with the soil level inside the enclosure. Additionally, during this general Victorian era, mortar was added in spots on the extant wall, likely in an attempt to prevent further deterioration of the wall. However, this mortar has dissolved over time, causing considerable deterioration in the extant wall where modified. Excavation in Cuttings C and Dn showed that the extant wall is barely supported by the stone, with most of the mortar washed away. Context 123 in 2022 was clearly a construction trench related to the addition of the mortar.

In all areas, the topsoil and turf were typically numbered as 1-100-200 over the three seasons. Some animal bone was found within these contexts, but the soil was also clearly churned, suggesting that some of the animal bones may be earlier than the Victorian era. Soderberg concluded that while some of the animal bone could be considered medieval based on taphonomy, the bones were found in proximity to clearly modern artifacts.

The artifact assemblage from this Victorian and modern phase included a large number of ceramic pipes. The majority of the pipes were located in an area to the north of the interior of the enclosure, near the entrance of the kitchen. A study of the pipes will be conducted in the next year. Champagne bottle fragments, jam jars, and a sardine tin key were found in this layer. Artifacts connecting the assemblage to the King family directly included a button from a servant jacket displaying the King family crest.

III. Animal Bone Assemblage Analysis

Dr. John Soderberg continues to conduct his analysis of the extensive collection of animal bones found during the three seasons of excavations. At this stage (the conclusion of our work in June 2024), he has completed the analysis of the 2019 and 2022 contexts. This constitutes over half the total assemblage, with the largest number of bones recovered in 2023.

Soderberg will provide a more detailed analysis based on his work later this summer. That more detailed report will incorporate the information from his interim report submitted in 2021 with additional data collected in Summer 2024. This summary includes data from analysis in 2021, 2022, and 2024.

Introduction

The 2019-2023 excavations on MacDermot's Rock on Lough Key, County Roscommon, revealed a high-status Gaelic lordly settlement from the high middle ages, along with evidence of a significant cashel-like fortification predating the high medieval settlement.

Results and Methodology

This analysis used various measures of abundance, including Number of Identified Specimens (NISP), Minimum Number of Elements (MNE), Minimum Number of Animal Units (MAU), and NISP-based MAU (MAU_NISP). Age was established using tooth wear and epiphyseal fusion, with data collected using Dibble and McPherron's database software. Surface modifications, pathologies, and other noteworthy features were recorded, and selected specimens were photographed and modeled using 3D photogrammetry.

General Results: Taphonomy and Preservation

Over 7,000 identified fragments were found in contexts from 2019 and 2022, with good preservation. However, a significant minority of bones showed evidence of staining, accretions, and surface degradation, suggesting different taphonomic histories, likely due to heat damage. Minimal evidence of carnivore gnawing and cutmarks was found, indicating limited pre-depositional taphonomic processes.

Fragmentation Rates and Species Ratio

Fragmentation rates were generally highest in C11, indicating intense processing. The species ratio was consistent across all non-modern contexts, with pigs being unusually prevalent compared to typical medieval sites, where cattle usually dominate. This

suggests a distinctive role for pigs at McDermot's Rock, possibly related to feasting and provisioning, similar to patterns seen at medieval castles.

Detailed Analysis of Cattle, Pig, and Sheep/Goat

Cattle

The cattle assemblage showed a broad representation of skeletal parts, with subtle differences in prevalence. The analysis revealed a negative relationship between food utility and element frequency, indicating that high utility elements were more intensively fragmented. The presence of unusually large proximal humeri suggested distinct taphonomic processes or selective deposition, possibly related to feasting.

Pig

All parts of the pig carcass were present, with some elements underrepresented. Age-at-death patterns were consistent with medieval Irish sites, with most pigs slaughtered in their first or second year. The analysis suggested a balanced representation of male and female pigs in most contexts. Notably, several pig specimens exhibited severe dental pathologies, possibly due to adverse living conditions.

Sheep/Goat

The sheep/goat assemblage was smaller, with all segments of the carcass represented. Age-at-death data indicated primarily mature individuals. Only one goat horn core was identified, suggesting limited presence on the island.

Metrical Data

The metrical data showed significant variation in cattle element dimensions, with cattle astragali being smaller than those from comparative sites, while proximal humeri were unusually large. Pig metric data also indicated generally smaller and more gracile specimens compared to other sites. The narrow range of pig acetabulum measurements suggested selective deposition.

Pathologies

Eight specimens exhibited pathologies, including osteophyte formation and dental pathologies, particularly among pigs. The high incidence of dental issues suggested adverse living conditions for pigs, possibly due to confinement or high densities.

Discussion

The McDermot's Rock animal bone assemblage offers valuable insights into the animal economy and political-economy of the region. The high prevalence of pigs aligns with patterns seen at medieval castles, suggesting significant feasting activities. The

anomalous taphonomic patterns, particularly heat damage, support the hypothesis of burning episodes. The metric data revealed unusual size patterns for cattle and pigs, suggesting selective deposition or distinct taphonomic processes.

Further research is needed to confirm these findings and expand the points of comparison, particularly with crannogs and other island settlements. Increasing the sample size through additional excavation is crucial for resolving key questions about the site's animal economy and its role in the broader landscape of Gaelic lordship.

IV. Recommendations for C14 Samples

At this stage of the post-excavation process we are confident of our chronology based upon contextual relationships and dating of various artifacts, including the dress pins, coins, and other items. Further confidence to the chronology will be gained by conducting C14 analysis on a sample of animal bones that have already been analyzed and that are deemed expendable. The project graciously accepted two C14 from the RIA-QUB scheme. Dr. John Soderberg has issued a statement attesting to the suitability of the samples and confirmation that the samples have already been analyzed and included in our database. Licenses to Export and Alter will be made to send these samples to QUB.

Context	Sample Number	Sample Type	Description
49	49:1	Pig tarsal	Fragment
274	274:!	Pig tibia	Burned pig fragment

Funding for additional samples was jointly provided by Saint Louis University and Denison University. All samples are animal bone fragments, and following the list is a statement from zooarchaeologist Dr. John Soderberg attesting to the suitability of the samples and confirmation that the samples have already been analyzed and included in our database. Licenses to Export and Alter have been made to send these samples to the University of Arizona C14 Lab.

Context	Sample Number	Sample Type	Description
25	25:1	Pig Tibia	Fragment
150	150:1	Cattle Rib	Fragment
159	159:1	Cattle Tibia	Fragment
223	223:1	Cattle Rib	Fragment
254	254:1	Pig Femur	Fragment
274	274:1	Pig Tibia	Burned pig fragments, likely tibia

V. Conclusions and Plans for Future Work

The Rock of Lough Key continues to be a remarkable site yielding a vast amount of new information related to high status settlement in the high medieval period. The results from this years effort all point to firm conclusion that the entire island is, for the most part, a medieval site, with a very slight Victorian veneer. Excavations and phasing on the interior of the island have shown that during the main phases of occupation in the early medieval and high medieval periods the site was a prominent fortification, and, more particularly in the high medieval period, was a site of production and feasting.

For the most part our analysis has focussed on the wealth of information resulting from the animal bone study. Thus far, there is a considerable amount of continuity across the site in terms of the butchering and consumption practices of the animals. Further analysis of this continuity is of course needed and will following in the next year as the remaining bones are studied.

While our focus has been on the nature of the animal bones as part of a feasting assemblage, we have also concluded that the bones and the industrial remains on the island are part of a production economy, with the animal bones not only used for consumption with feasting but also the production of high status goods for entertainment. Many of the artifacts found were in process, meaning that we not only found the products (like dice), but the materials leading to the products (like die molds). The area of industrial activity has been found to date to the high medieval period, and a number of crucibles were located in that area; this is an area of further needed analysis.

The artifact assemblage continues to move through processing, with the 2019 artifacts conserved and deposited with the National Museum. These artifacts will be labeled in January, 2025. The artifacts from 2022 and 2023 are in the process of being conserved and upon completion will be integrated with the 2019 finds. The animal bones (again, half completed) will be deposited in total at the discretion of the National Museum.

Appendix I: Sample of Artifacts

Pottery Fragments, Green Glaze

Copper Bucket Handle, Note Triangle Design on Left

Silver Dress Pin, Square Top, hatch decoration on shaft

Bone Gaming Piece

Iron Handle

Crucible Fragment

Iron Sheers

Appendix II: Temporary Site Plan based upon New Phasing, Cuttings A, B, C, F

Phase I: Entrance Feature

Phase 4: Pavement

Phase 3: Cashel Wall

Phase 4: Building Walls, Clay Floor C4
not depicted

Phase 4: Entrance Feature

Appendix III: Geological Survey

Geology - McDermott's Castle, Lough Key.

- 20 samples examined. 9/20 show evidence of water erosion, most likely lakeshore.
- Four main geological units identified from these 20 samples.
- Geological Survey of Ireland (GSI) published map and rock unit descriptions reviewed.
- Three shore locations visited to verify published geological map.
- **Conclusion:** Examined samples are consistent with collection from shore from different locations on lake.
 - Most likely rocks were collected from different locations depending on which farmer was tasked with the job and/or from what direction the wind was blowing.

Conclusions and Recommendations

- Examined samples are consistent with collection from shore from different locations on lake.
- Most likely rocks were collected from different locations depending on which farmer was tasked with the job and/or from what direction the wind was blowing.
- Geo map is not perfect at the scale examined. 2/3 locations checked were different to published info. This is not surprising at the scale the mapping was conducted (especially with fault running quite near to lake shore in this area.)
- Unit 52 the continental red beds may in fact crop out at a location nearer than on the current map. Ground truthing kayak or paddle board or other very shallow craft is a simple way to check.
- On balance most of these samples could just as easily be dug out from the lake shore as truly 'quarried'.
- Due to the obvious human transport of rock onto the Island and time constraints, no attempt was made to find the true bedrock of the Island.
- This would require trenching down to true bedrock. Preferably, in several locations. Based on ground truthing of the published map, I won't be surprised to find out that the Island is part of a fault splay and has two of these units in the bedrock as a result

Appendix IV: Rock of Lough Key Shore Aerial Survey

Lake levels on the Rock of Lough Key were at an unprecedented low level during June, 2024, allowing for significant survey of the shore to the south of the Rock of Lough Key. The harbor built for the Rockingham estate, still used by Lough Key Boats and the marina in general, significantly altered the shore in that south west corner; further, the line of finished stone extending from the harbor to the boat drop is all part of the Rockingham harbor. To the east of the small viewing tower, however, the shore is likely natural in most respects. Aerial survey of this area showed stone that corresponds to both the Geological Survey in Appendix III, and also analysis of the stone on the Rock.

Shoreline, with evidence of quarrying

Same shore, extending to second Rockingham Pier

Northern End of Causeway with Green Island at the top

Medieval Pier Noted by O'Connor from 2008; what is curious to note is the similarity between this pier and the piers/slips on the Rock

Appendix V: Lough Key Shore Survey, East of Castle Island

An underwater survey carried out by Niall Brady in 2008 suggested a number of underwater features associated with the Rock of Lough Key, including a midden on the exterior of the Victorian era kitchen. Aerial photos in 2019 revealed what is interpreted as a winding causeway from the island to Green Island. Lake elevations and atmospheric conditions were excellent for photography and additional analysis in 2024.

A more detailed plan of the area is being prepared.

Line of stones from Rock of Lough Key

Causeway from Rock to Green Island, with possible slip or pier

Appendix VI: Extant Wall Collapse

The precarious nature of the ruins on the Rock of Lough Key continue to be a concern. The Nash additions to the tower house are of particular concern, with whole segments breaking away from the core tower house. But of more immediate concern is the collapse of the extant wall on the western side of the island. This wall, probably modified during the 19th century in order to give the large picture windows a better view, included a toilet tower and the added crenelations as the rest of the extant wall. In the winter of 2020, a northerly storm battered the island at this point, and as a result the wall (including the toilet tower) collapsed outward.

The collapse created a rubble spread on the shore, with the clear evidence of Victorian modifications as part of the collapse. Upon cleaning this area, though, several additional features were noted in the extant wall that would suggest an earlier, medieval origin for the wall, including a plinth at the base of the wall.

Of greater concern, though, is that the standing wall that did not collapse shows a fracture that is three to four centimeters wide, and offset from the wall. Additionally, from the 2022 excavations, we know that this area is essentially without significant support, given that the mortar placed in the 19th century has disappeared. In other words, I am very concerned about the stability of the *entire* wall on this side, and would argue that it needs attention very soon in order to prevent a massive collapse. At the same time, this area is of significance stratigraphically, as it is probably the only spot on the island where we might be able to analyze the fill between the extant wall and the *cashel* wall.

APPENDIX A
PHOTOGRAPHS